

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDEKSIA SOUMAI****FIRST NAME: ESTHER****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

IMPORTANT THINGS TO KNOW FOR AN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

An essay writing must be international, because worldwide people have to read and have the same understanding. This mean that the basics of essay writing must be well done. When I began with the Doctorate International Public Health program, I would not imagine that the first course will be about academic writing, in my mind, this course will be at the end of the program. My surprise lets place to an excitation when I was looked after the materials send to me. The first thing I saw was the video about the Zotero's application, and then I read the ACA-401D coursepack. This course teaches me about the important things to know when writing a paper. It is not possible to become a good written without assimilate it.

2) DIFFERENT STEPS OF AN ESSAY WRITING

Refers to EUCLID, an academic writing must follow different basic steps, that is starting the essay by finding the answer of the question and constructing the initial plan (EUCLID 2015, 2). The question asked by the author may have many answers but finding what I will called the 'right answer' is what will orientate your work.

Your starting point for an essay is your initial response to the topic or question. This response is based on what you already know. However, this is only the starting point. You then need to research, question your response and find some answers (EUCLID 2015, 2).

a) Starting the essay

The error we make frequently is to wait the last time or the end of a work to start writing it down, we think that waiting enough idea is the best, however 'you can't write a successful essay unless you give yourself enough time to read' (EUCLID 2005, 2). Personally, I am the example of not starting early. EUCLID tell us that 'an academic essay should answer a question or task' (EUCLID 2015, 2). When I look about paper we are writing, I find that the question is sometimes asked after the essay is written. This made us to orient the questions to the answer; it is not the best thing to do. Logically, when we try to answer a question, the ideas are larger, and the development is more interesting. The first thing is to 'define the question and analyze the task' (EUCLID 2015, 2).

b) Reading list

If you are not a good reader, you cannot be a good writer. 'A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researcher.' (EUCLID 2015,3). It is essential for the writer to know what the other persons think about the subject, it could not be easy to develop something that you do not have the most of information. By reading, you must 'make notes from the readings' (EUCLID 2015, 3).

Sometimes, when you read about a subject, the first idea you have on the subject change and you start to consider other options. I like reading, because it is like having a discuss with people around the world and not looking for period. It is good to discover what someone think about the subject in the last century and how things are changed by time. So, it is also important to read because of discussing your idea, find the evidence and the opposite of what you argue.

c) The essay plans

The essay plans are what will orientate the work. 'After you've researched and your ideas are more developed, write a second essay plan' (EUCLID 2015, 3). I discover that with more information about a subject, it is easier to write a plan and to decide how the different themes will be arranging. This plan 'will help you work out how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured' (EUCLID 2015, 3). I was particularly interest with the way we must draw up the second plan: 'Decide on a possible answer to the question (in terms of the research you have done), decide on the information you will use to answer the question, look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer' (EUCLID 2015, 3). The analyze is now possible with all the information in front of us.

d) Drafting and structure

Making a draft is to write the first line of the essay. 'Once you have a draft, you can work on writing well' (EUCLID 2015, 4). The standard's structure is made up an introduction, a body and a conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 4). Understanding that the body is develop with the main point I find in my researches and that have been arrange in a plan.

e) Referencing the essay

When I was reading the coursepack, I found that 'when writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is to avoid Plagiarism' (EUCLID 2015, 7). In our world today, everyone use internet to be inspire for papers; and the things we do is to copy and paste, without cite the source of the work. After reading EUCLID, I understand that this procedure is plagiarism, and I must avoid it (EUCLID 2015, 7).

Moreover, not giving credit to the author, is found because we do not know how to cite. EUCLID shows how to cite; In-text citation 'refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself' (EUCLID 2015, 16).

In my experience, I have learned to use List of Works Cited as references at the end of the book. But it is with EUCLID that I learned about the difference to use Footnotes and Endnotes with 'Word 2007' (EUCLID 2015, 36).

3) STYLE GUIDE

Before reading the coursepack, I have no idea about the style. The only thing I learned was the difference between US and UK. But now I find that there is a style guide that is not only the spelling, it is 'a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent' (EUCLID 2015, 52). The EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules. The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) provides information about the Chicago Style and Usage, the Chicago Formatting and the Chicago End/Footnotes. I learned that there is difference between abbreviations and acronyms, acronyms are abbreviations, but all abbreviations are not acronyms, and there is a rule to report them in a text. Scholarly abbreviations are only use in a text if put in brackets (EUCLID 2015, 52).

4) CONCLUSION

It was a wonderful experience for me, reading the coursepack ACA-401D period one and watching the video provide by the course. Many information come from it like how to write an essay, the style to use, avoiding plagiarism and making references. There is something that I have to make it many times to be familiar with it, but I know that after this period, the way I write a paper has definitely change.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed December 29, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.